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Digital Cloud Computing and Marketing Skills Required of Office Technology and Management Education Graduates for Global Relevance

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ABSTRACT

This study examined digital cloud computing and marketing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was one thousand, one hundred and twenty seven (1127) Directors and Administrative officers in Delta State Civil Service in Delta State. The sample size of 295 directors and administrative officers was used. A structured questionnaire containing 61 items entitled “Digital Skills Required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance Questionnaire (DSROTMEGGRQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three (3) experts. The Cronbach Alpha Reliability coefficient was 0.94. One hundred and forty five (145) copies of instrument were administered to the respondents, 123 copies representing 93% were successfully retrieved from Business Educators. Mean (X) and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool. Findings of the study revealed that Office Technology and Management Education graduates highly required digital cloud computing skills, and marketing skills for global relevance. Findings also revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the digital foundation skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of highly experienced and less experienced respondents on the digital software management skills required of office technology and management education graduate for global relevance. The study concluded that digital skills were very much needed by office technology and management education graduates for global relevance. Finally the study recommended among others that National University Commission/Universities and National Colleges of Education (NCCE) Curriculum planners of office technology and management education programme should include cloud computing courses into technology and management curriculum so that lecturers can impart students cloud computing skills to the student

Keywords: Digital skills, Office Technology and Management Education, Global relevance.

INTRODUCTION

In this modern world, fast changes have taken place in all facets of human life, including the office environment, due to global technological advancement. Modern business offices (government or private) require effective and efficient information for better decision-making. The processing of information and management functions in various offices rest mainly on the secretaries, who are office information managers. Therefore, the management of any organisation expects office technology management graduates in their domain to possess relevant digital skills to perform office functions effectively and efficiently.

Digital skills refer to the skills needed for the use of digital devices, communication applications and networks to access and manage information, from basic online searching and emailing to specialist programming and development (Norris, 2019). Digital skills refer to those skills needed by individuals to use digital devices, communication applications, and networks to access and manage information (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), 2018). They enable individuals to create and share digital content, communicate and collaborate with others and solve problems for effective and creative self-fulfillment in life, learning, work, and social activities at large. According to Okeji, Nwankwo, Anene and Olorunfemi (2020), digital skills represent a set of skills needed to effectively and efficiently perform office tasks using new technologies in the digital environment. The United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) (2019) stated that any definition of digital skills should involve the ability to confidently, critically and responsibly use and engage digital technologies for learning, at work, and for participation in 21st century society. In the context of this study, digital skills are the abilities of using digital technologies to transform existing traditional and non-digital business processes and services, or create new ones, to meet evolving market and customer expectations. Some digital skills are required of office managers to be able to carry out some specific tasks, while others are required to design, create and maintain tools and solutions for different industries. To this end, the Digital Marketing Institute (2017) suggested that jobseekers (Office Technology and Management graduates inclusive) require such specialised digital skills to help them stand out from the crowd for global relevance.

Global relevance refers to the ability of Office Technology and Management Education graduates to compete with their counterparts internationally. In the context of this study, global relevance refers to when a graduate can develop competent digital skills that will enable graduate develop and manage business ideas that meet international standard. Office Technology and Management (OTM) is a programme in business education. According to Ezenwafor and Onokpaunu (2017), business education programme is a branch of vocational education concerned with exposing its recipients to the internal and external foundations and functioning of the workplace. One of the main objectives of business education is to empower students with desirable skills, knowledge and values to become gainfully employed or self-reliant upon graduation (Nwagu & Nwankwo, 2016). Business education has three major specialised subject areas: accounting education, office technology and management education, marketing education and entrepreneurship education. According to Oyinkoye and Oluwalola (2020), Office Technology and Management Education is a nomenclature that emerged and replaced the former Secretarial Studies Programme and was introduced by the National Board for Technical Education in 2004. They emphasised that the replacement is meant to make the programme and its recipients more ICT-compliant and to adequately fit into the world of work, where equipment and new machines are emerging daily. Office Technology and Management Education (OTME) is an aspect of the business education programme, a specialised course of study offered in colleges of education and universities (Olumese and Ediagbonya, 2016). The Office Technology and Management Education curriculum is aimed at producing graduates who would be able to effectively manage the electronic-driven office and be equipped with secretarial and office skills for employment in various fields of endeavour. Yamme (2020) noted that modern offices are equipped with brand new business models, complex technologies, and the right digital tools that connect and support employees for improved productivity. Olukemi and Boluwaji (2018) defined OTM as the application of scientific knowledge, devices, and systems to

facilitate and enhance the information processes and delivery of the same. It is also viewed as a concept that is associated with office automation, electronic technology, and office globalisation. Office Technology and Management is a course of study in Nigerian tertiary institutions designed to replace the secretarial studies programme. The need to prepare and make students of secretarial studies to be competent, skilled, and employable in the world of work gave birth to Office Technology and Management which is being driven by technological content in the curriculum of the programme in the nation's tertiary institutions.

Office Technology and Management Education graduates are a class of graduates who have gone through either a three- or four-year programme of study in the content of the business education curriculum. A student admitted into the college of education is expected to complete the programme in three academic years (six semesters), while at the university level, the students have the opportunity to complete the programme in four academic years (eight semesters). However, the programme is more practical inclined, with the students' involvement in the Students' Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), Teaching Practice (TP), and in-house practicals as prerequisite for attaining individual and organisational performance. Based on this training programme, Office Technology and Management Education graduates are expected to possess the up-to-date competencies required for job performance. The possession of appropriate competencies would offer Office Technology and Management graduates a unique strategy for job performance.

Some employers have tried to outline some of the skills they want from job seekers. In a bid to creating harmony in their skills, the Secretary, Commission on Achieving Necessary Skills (SCANS), prepared reports on ways of assisting educational institutions and schools in producing younger generations who are willing to work globally. The report outlines both fundamental skills and workplace competencies to include: basic thinking, personal qualities, resources, interpersonal information, digital skills (SCANS, 2021). The above skills are no doubt invaluable to technology and management education graduates. According to Olorok (2022), The Chartered Institute of Personnel Management of Nigeria has advocated a drastic change in the mentality of job-seeking youths in the country by striving to become potential job seekers of global relevance. From their investigation, they have put the percentage of unemployed graduates from Nigerian institutions of higher learning to be 80 percent. This goes to send a very bad signal to the nation that the rate of graduate unemployment is very alarming.

Same can be said about Delta State where there is a high level of graduate unemployment. This is because skills possessed by Office Technology and Management Education graduates seem to be different from what the employers want. Nwokocha (2021), noted that the goal of business education (Office Technology and Management inclusive), is the production of manpower, who possesses the requisite knowledge, skills and attitudes for harnessing other resources and bringing them together into a cooperative relationship yielding the goods and services demanded by the society for the satisfaction of their wants and needs. Thus, the student must acquire the digital skills needed to integrate management, marketing, accounting, finance and education concepts to be able to compete globally in the work place.

Presently, many organisations are recognising the importance of digital skills for graduates to fit into modern offices. Burton (2021) stated that digital skills make an organisation a freer and simpler place to work. A lot of organisations' work can now be done from home. Consumers now expect more from an organisation, knowing that technology has made everything so much faster. It is more important than ever for graduates of tertiary institutions to possess a range of digital skills that will enhance their employment potentials. In support of this view, Berger and Frey (2016) pointed out that the kinds of digital skills required of graduates of higher institutions change over time in line with changes in technologies. Berger and Frey asserted that as new technologies emerge, narrow technical skills become insufficient for many emerging jobs while the demand for higher-level digital skills increases.

Digital skills needed by graduates of tertiary institutions in the modern workplace can include information and data skills, digital safety skills, cloud computing skills, word processing skills, spreadsheet skills and internet skills. Round (2018) listed types of digital skills as basic digital skills, digital skills for the general labour force, and digital skills for ICT professionals. Similarly, the Department of Education

(2018) enumerated digital foundation skills, communication skills, information and content handling skills, and problem-solving skills as major types of digital skills. Additionally, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) (2018) stated that digital skills are divided into three levels: basic digital skills, intermediate digital skills, and advanced digital skills. Office Technology and Management graduates are expected to acquire these digital skills which are Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in nature for economic survival which include; digital foundation skills, software management and digital marketing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates.

The term cloud refers to a network or the internet. It is a technology that uses remote servers on the internet to store, manage, and access data online rather than local drives. The data can be anything such as files, images, documents, audio, video, and more. Cloud computing is a virtualization-based technology that allows us to create, configure, and customize applications via an internet connection. Cloud computing according to Kazarian and Hannon, (2021) is a service that provides users to work over the internet. Users can access data on the Cloud and must provide a user ID and password to gain entry, for security reasons. Cloud computing according to Saidhbi (2018), is a kind of computing resources which facilitates sharing of resources and services over the internet rather than having these services and resources on local servers/nodes or personal devices. Haghghat, Zonouz, and AbdelMottaleb, (2015) opined that there are three service models of Cloud Computing namely - Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Software as a Service (SaaS). IaaS offers necessary computing resources like processing, storage, networks and operating resources over the internet. PaaS offers platform referees to Google App Engine to run the user created or acquired applications on the internet. SaaS provides applications and software (Google Docs) on cloud which can be accessed through any device having web browser (Kazarian and Hannon, 2021).

Digital-marketing is another name for electronic or digital marketing. It is a part of digital marketing system introduced by the presence of digital technology. As new concept in marketing it has broad definitions as conceived by authors. Sometimes it is used interchangeable with online, internet or web marketing. Azubuike (2017) described electronic marketing as a computerized marketing process involving planning and executing the conception, distribution, promotion and pricing of products and services using internet and the World Wide Web environment to enable the exchange and satisfy customers' demand. Turban (2020) asserted e-marketing to be a process of buying, selling, transferring, serving, or exchanging products, services, or information via computer network and the Internet facilities. Gilmore (2017) argued that e-marketing process involves delivering values to customers through internet and other technological tools.

These new methods of performing office duties as a result of technological changes in the office environment call for adequate training and preparation of prospective graduates especially in Office Technology and Management Education, to acquire the knowledge, skills, competencies, and experiences needed to perform above board in 21st century modern offices. This is because no worker excels in the workplace without adequate and relevant digital skills. Ojo and Akhademe (2016) stated that OTME programmes are designed to equip students with office skills such as knowledge, skills, and competencies that will enable them to successfully hold positions as secretaries, managers and secretarial administrators in both the public and private sectors of the economy for employment in various fields of human endeavour. It also exposes students to industrial experiences, thereby affording them the opportunity to practicalize their skills and develop in them occupational intelligence that will make them versatile and adaptable to changing situations in the world of work. To achieve these objectives, the OTME curriculum at the college of education and university levels must emphasise and inculcate in the students employability skills that are relevant and required to function effectively in this modern-day technological world. The assessment of digital skills by employers of labour may be influenced by their gender and years of working experience.

Work experience is the practical experience gained with an employer by learning about a particular role, organisation or career path (Indeed Career Guide, 2021). Years of work experience matter a lot in the

workplace. According to Helyer and Lee (2018), work experience enhances employability. Furthermore, it is generally believed that the more years one has on a job, the more effective one is in performing the job. This could be attributed to differences in training and other experiences, which may lead to the acquisition of different digital skills. Gude (2018) asserted that as employees work continuously for a long time on a particular task, they develop relevant skills for high performance. It may also be possible that the number of years an employer has had on the job may influence his or her digital skills for the employment of Office Technology and Management Education graduates. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) (2018) defined gender as the roles and responsibilities of men and women that are created in families, societies and cultures. Muhammad (2019) opined that gender could influence capacity to acquire digital skills. In this regard, gender, could influence employers' ratings of the digital skills required of Office technology and management graduates for global relevance. Wickramasinghe and Perera (2020) noted that the gender of students may also influence the types of soft skills that are provided to them. This is because the priorities given to different types of skills vary according to the gender of the students. Wickramasinghe and Perera posited that overall, female students place stronger emphasis than male students on most types of soft skills, with the exception of oral communication skills.

This is because the priorities given to different types of skills vary according to the gender of the students. Wickramasinghe and Perera posited that overall, female students place stronger emphasis than male students on most types of digital skills, with the exception of oral communication skills. It is against this background that this study explored the digital skills required by Office Technology and Management Education students for global relevance in Delta State.

Statement of the Problem

This current relevance of global skills is underpinned by international economic competition, advances in technology, and greater diversity and mobility, all resulting from a more globalized world. Increasingly, the graduates of the OTME programme need to recognize that digital skills are crucial for success in the workplace and society at large. Possession of global relevant skills by prospective graduating students, especially the graduates of the OTME programme from colleges of education and universities is essential for effective job performance. However, the researcher observed that OTME students do not graduate with adequate skills that are needed for employment in today's modern office. It has been discovered that: over 40 million graduates are unemployable in the industries because of lack of technical and digital skills required for available jobs (Audu, Abdulkadir, & Abdul 2017). This implies that there is insignificance in the digital skills acquired in the programme offered in schools to the employment needs of individual learners. Based on this, there is a need for the OTME programme to accommodate adequate and relevant skills that will enhance the competencies, knowledge, and abilities of the students to be able to fit into the 21st century office, perform optimally and be self employed. In Delta State, there seems to be limited research on the digital skills required of business education graduates for global relevance. Therefore, it is pertinent for the study to determine the digital skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates in Delta State for global relevance.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the digital skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance. Specifically, the study ascertained:

1. The digital cloud computing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance.
2. The digital marketing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the digital cloud computing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance?

2. What are the digital marketing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean of respondents on the digital foundation skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance based on gender.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of respondents on the digital software management skills required of office technology and management education graduate for global relevance based on work experiences.

METHOD

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for the study was one thousand, one hundred and twenty seven (1127) Directors and Administrative officers in Delta State Civil Service in Delta State. The sample size of 295 directors and administrative officers was used through Yaro Yemeni formular. A structured questionnaire containing 22 items entitled “Digital Skills Required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance Questionnaire (DSROTMEGGRQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three (3) experts. The instrument was administered to 30 directors and administrative officers in Anambra State civil service in a trial-testing. This was to avoid the interaction with the instrument by the subjects of the study in Delta State. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient method. Cronbach Alpha Reliability coefficient obtained was 0.94. One hundred and forty five (145) copies of instrument were administered to the respondents, 123 copies representing 93% were successfully retrieved from Business Educators. Mean (X) and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool. The result of hypotheses tested with t-test was accepted when the calculated p-value is greater than the selected level of significance at 0.05 and rejected when the calculated p-value is less than the selected level of significance at 0.05.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What are the clouds computing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance in Delta State?*

Data providing answers to the above research question are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Clouds Computing Skills Required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance

S/N	Items	N	Mean	Std.	Decision
1	use internet to maintain shared document	235	3.30	.766	Highly Required
2	use central remote servers to maintain shared document	235	3.44	.588	Highly Required
3	store files using Google docs,	235	3.39	.627	Highly Required
4	share files using instant messaging service	235	3.36	.714	Highly Required
5	store files using dropBox	235	3.36	.689	Highly Required
6	store files using Google drive	235	3.35	.637	Highly Required
7	mark files for destruction in the cloud	235	3.36	.681	Highly Required
8	Preserve electronic records using emulation	235	3.30	.739	Highly Required
9	Preserve electronic records using cloud	235	3.39	.663	Highly Required
10	Scan document	235	3.40	.554	Highly Required
11	Design coding methodology	235	3.45	.573	Highly Required
	Grand Mean		3.35		Highly Required

Data in Table 1 shows that all the 11 listed items on cloud computing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance have mean scores that ranged from 3.22 – 3.43 which fall above the real limit of 2.50. This indicates that all the items on cloud computing skills are required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance. The standard deviation of the eight items ranges from .554 to .766 indicating that the mean scores of the responses are close to each other.

Research Questions Two: *What are the digital marketing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance in Delta State?*

Data providing answers to the above research question are presented in Table 2 below

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Digital Marketing Skills Required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance

S/N	Items	N	Mean	Std.	Decision
12	Use the electronic mail to mail business content	235	3.26	.742	Highly Required
13	design business logo using digital application	235	3.35	.628	Highly Required
14	design product services catalogues	235	3.26	.663	Highly Required
15	Access information from customers' through internet	235	3.24	.675	Highly Required
16	Compose business content to attract customers	235	3.29	.649	Highly Required
17	Retrieve business content	235	3.25	.687	Highly Required
18	Use e-mail to direct customers to business shops	235	3.19	.673	Highly Required
19	Use electronic devices to create content marketing	235	3.33	.637	Highly Required
20	Use hubspot as marketing strategy	235	3.27	.631	Highly Required
21	Do on-line marketing	235	3.36	.578	Highly Required
22	undertake market segmentation Via the internet	235	3.18	.724	Highly Required
23	Browse internet searching for customers	235	3.24	.653	Highly Required
24	Goods and services through social media	235	3.13	.724	Highly Required
25	Use interactive multimedia technologies for marketing	235	3.28	.644	Highly Required
26	conduct e-transactions	235	3.26	.699	Highly Required
Grand Mean			3.48		Highly Required

Data in Table 2 shows that all the 15 listed items on digital marketing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance have mean scores that ranged from 3.15 – 3.37 which fall above the real limit of 2.50. This indicates that all the items on digital marketing skills are required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance. The standard deviation of the eight items ranges from .628 to 0.742 indicating that the mean scores of the responses are close to each other.

Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents on the digital cloud computing skills required of office technology and management education graduate for global relevance by location.

Table 3: Independent t-test of Mean Ratings of Responses of Rural and Urban Respondents on the digital cloud computing Skills Required of Office Technology and Management Education Graduate for Global Relevance.

Location	N	Mean	Std.	DF	Alpha	p-val.	Decision
Urban	162	3.48	.562				
Rural	73	3.12	.813	233	0.05	.018	Significant
Urban	162	3.45	.505				
Rural	73	3.43	.621	233	0.05	.831	Not significant
Urban	162	3.48	.507				
Rural	73	3.29	.663	233	0.05	.129	Not significant
Urban	162	3.48	.562				
Rural	73	3.23	.758	233	0.05	.083	Not significant
Urban	162	3.40	.650				
Rural	73	3.32	.706	233	0.05	.611	Not significant
Urban	162	3.37	.689				
Rural	73	3.32	.620	233	0.05	.744	Not Significant
Urban	162	3.45	.657				
Rural	73	3.26	.686	233	0.05	.151	Not significant
Urban	162	3.45	.560				
Rural	73	3.15	.786	233	0.05	.043	Significant
Urban	162	3.51	.507				
Rural	73	3.27	.706	233	0.05	.068	Not Significant
Urban	162	3.42	.557				
Rural	73	3.38	.555	233	0.05	.705	Not significant
Urban	162	3.51	.507				
Rural	73	3.39	.597	233	0.05	.311	Not significant
Urban	162						
Rural	73			233	0.05	.335	Not significant

Summary of result on Table 3 indicates that ten (10) out of twelve items have their P- values ranging from 0.068 to 0.831 which are greater than 0.05 indicating no significant difference in the mean responses of urban and rural respondents on the digital cloud computing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduate for global relevance. While item 36 and 43 only has P-value of 0.025 which is less than 0.05 indicating a significant difference in the mean rating responses of respondents on the cloud computing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduate for global relevance based on location. The overall P-value 0.468 is greater than 0.05, indicates that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents on the digital cloud computing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduate for global relevance by location is not rejected.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents on the digital marketing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduate for global relevance by gender.

Table 4: Independent t-test of Mean Ratings of Responses Respondents on the Digital Marketing Skills Required of Office Technology and Management Education Graduate for Global Relevance by Gender

Summary of result in Table 4 indicates that fourteen (14) out of fifteen (15) items have their P- values ranging from 0.136 to 0.818 which are greater than 0.05 indicating no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents on the digital marketing skills required of office technology and management

Gender	N	Mean	Std.	Df	Alpha	p-val.	Decision
Male	130	3.18	.761				
Female	105	3.34	.710	233	0.05	.230	Not significant
Male	130	3.38	.594				
Female	105	3.32	.677	233	0.05	.644	Not significant
Male	130	3.28	.589				
Female	105	3.23	.757	233	0.05	.676	Not significant
Male	130	3.33	.631				
Female	105	3.15	.724	233	0.05	.136	Not significant
Male	130	3.23	.642				
Female	105	3.36	.657	233	0.05	.290	Not significant
Male	130	3.30	.623				
Female	105	3.19	.767	233	0.05	.351	Not Significant
Male	130	3.18	.703				
Female	105	3.21	.636	233	0.05	.818	Not significant
Male	130	3.38	.594				
Female	105	3.28	.695	233	0.05	.433	Not significant
Male	130	3.28	.565				
Female	105	3.26	.717	233	0.05	.914	Not significant
Male	130	3.43	.527				
Female	105	3.28	.636	233	0.05	.161	Not significant
Male	130	3.15	.710				
Female	105	3.21	.749	233	0.05	.670	Not significant
Male	130	3.21	.630				
Female	105	3.26	.689	233	0.05	.629	Not significant
Male	130	3.29	.724				
Female	105	2.96	.684	233	0.05	.011	Significant
Male	130	3.25	.648				
Female	105	3.30	.642	233	0.05	.647	Not significant
Male	130	3.26	.696				
Female	105	3.25	.710	233	0.05	.891	Not significant
				233	0.05	.500	Not significant

education graduates for global relevance by gender. The overall P-value 0.500 is greater than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents on the digital marketing skills required of office technology and management education graduate for global relevance by gender is not rejected.

DISCUSSION

Findings of the study revealed that cloud computing skills are highly required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance. This indicated that ability to use internet to maintain shared document, use central remote servers to maintain shared documents, store files using Google docs, share files using instant messaging services, store files using dropBox, store files using Google drive, mark files for destruction in the cloud, Preserve electronic records using emulation, scan documents and design coding methodology are cloud computing skills highly required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance.

The findings agreed with the findings of Adozoga and Massnawain Ezeonwurie (2017), who identified cloud computer skills required of OTM graduates to include proficient in word-processing spreadsheet and desktop publishing software including sending and receiving electronic mails (e-mail) and browsing the world wide Web (www) (that is the internet). The finding is also in agreement with the finding of Berger and Frey (2016) who found that new technologies emerge; narrow technical skills become insufficient for many emerging jobs while the demand for higher level digital office skills increases. Berger and Frey (2016) further found that digital skills needed by graduates of office technology and management in the modern workplace to give a decent work include information and data skills, digital safety skills, cloud computing skills, word processing skills, spreadsheet skills, and internet skills. The finding is also in line with the study of Offili (2017) who found that digitally skilled employee that want a decent work in the global office, should have the skills to use computer, desktop and laptop computers and other electronic devices to complete office tasks. The employee should also be able to objectively analyze facts to form accurate judgement, think critically, develop the ability to engage in online community meetings and social media network and possess the capacity to understand the emerging societal issues caused by the evolution of digital technologies.

The researcher is of the view that the results is so because digitalization now the major driver in today's global economy has become one of the most sought after skill-sets of the 21st century. The internet is now the new and obviously the biggest market place worldwide, and digital skills are the key to unlocking the potentials in this new market place. The global market system of today needs new sets of skills for marketing, advertising and business promotional activities necessary for setting-up, growing and effective management of businesses. Students need full range of such digital skills in order to meaningfully participate in the 21st century global economy.

The findings on the hypothesis tested showed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of urban and rural respondents on the digital cloud computing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance. The findings agreed with the findings of Braesemann, Lehdonvirta and Kassi (2020) who said rural workers to be disproportionate in the use of the ICT tools compared to those in urban. In a similar investigation conducted by Imai and Malaeb (2017), it was found that inequality and rural-urban disparity exist in more complex ways including the use of ICT which is in favour of the urban. The findings is also in line with the findings of Wang (2017) who also found that there is a difference in overall high-tech integration level between rural and urban institutions of learning. The implication of the findings is that location of organization does not have influence on the digital cloud computing skills required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance.

Findings showed that digital marketing skills are highly required of Office Technology and Management Education graduates for global relevance. This means that ability to use the electronic mail to mail business content, design business logo using digital application, design product services catalogues, access information from customers' through internet, compose business content to attract customers, retrieve business content, use e-mail to direct customers to business shops, use electronic devices to create content marketing, use hubspot as marketing strategy, do on-line marketing, undertake market segmentation via the internet, browse internet searching for customers, goods and services through social media, use interactive multimedia technologies for marketing and conduct e-transactions are digital marketing skills highly required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance.

The findings was supported by Barrett (2022) who stated that digital marketing skills include writing and editing, search engine optimization, design skills, social paid advertising, top-notch personal brand, wordpress, excel proficiency, social media marketing, email marketing and Makosiewicz (2022) who noted that data literacy, understanding different marketing. They also agreed with channels, copywriting, getting around essential digital marketing tools, basic design skills, communication skills, content creation, customer relationship management are digital marketing skills among others.

The researcher is of the opinion that the results are so because in today's business environment demand that business-related students acquire ICT competencies to enable them compete favourably with others in the global labour market.

Furthermore, the test of the fifth hypothesis tested showed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female respondents on the digital marketing skills required of office technology and management education graduates for global relevance. This finding corroborated the findings of Umeano (2021) that male and female lecturers did not differ significantly in their mean rating of digital skills needed by business education graduates for employability in North- East Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings and discussion of this study it is concluded that cloud computing and marketing skills are very much needed by office technology and management education students for global relevance in the world of work. The implication is that inculcation of the essential skills in business education curriculum will enable the recipients to function effectively for global relevance in the world of work. This is very essential for the continued relevance and survival of business education graduates in the digital era.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. National University Commission/Universities and National Colleges of Education (NCCE) Curriculum planners of office technology and management education programme should include cloud computing courses into technology and management curriculum so that lecturers can impart students cloud computing skills to the student
2. A course on digital marketing skills acquisition should be introduced to final year students offering office technology and management education in all tertiary institution by curriculum planners in order for them to fit into the digital workplace environment after graduation.

REFERENCES

- Akudolu, V. J. & Onyeneka, K. (2021). Digital skill gap among business education graduates of tertiary institutions in Anambra state: implication for programme re-adjustment. *Nigerian Communication and Information Technology Journal*, 1(2), 10-19.
- Audu, G. N Abdulkadir, I. S. & Abdul, J. L. (2017). Strategies for enhancing the teaching of ICT in business education programmes as perceived by business education lecturers in universities in South – South Nigeria. *International Education Studies*, 6 (10), 78-89.
- Berger, S. K. & Frey, H. (2016). The role of information communication technology in Nigeria educational system. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*, (2)2, 64-68
- Burton, F. P (2021). The Importance of digital skills in the modern workplace. Retrieved from: <https://www.skillsyouneed.com/rhubarb/digitalskills-modern-workplace.html>
- Department of Education (2018). Bridging the digital gender divide-include, upskill, innovate, <http://www.Oecd.org/internet/bridging-the-digital-gender-divide.pdf>
- Digital Marketing Institute (2017, July 11). 10 digital skills that can make students instantly employable. [Web log post]. Retrieved from <https://digitalmarketinginstitute.com/blog/10-digital-skills-that-can-make-students-instantly-employable>
- Dixon. J. A. (2019). What are digital foundation skills and why do they matter? Retrieved from: <https://www.youthemployment.org.uk/what-are-digital-foundation-skills-and-why-do-they-matter/>
- Edet, E. O. (2019). Electronic-based learning resources required in business education and skill acquisition for global business environment. *Nigerian Journal of Business Educators*. 6(2), 163-172

- Egbunefu, G. A. , & Ubani, G. F. (2022). Business education perception of digital skills needed for effective performance in the world of work. *KWASU International Journal of Education (KIJE)* 5 (1), 155-165
- Ezenwafor, J. I & Onokpaunu, C. N. (2017). *Digital skills critical for jobs and social inclusion*. Retrieved from: <https://en.unesco.org/news/digital-skills-critical-jobs-and-social-inclusion/View-publication>
- Ezenwafor, J. I. & Garba, J. L. (2020)*Digital Skills for Learning, Life and Work (N.D)*. Retrieved from: <https://educationbusinessuk.net/features/digital-skills-learning-life-and-work/> April 11th, 2022
- Ezenwafor, J. I. & Olaniyi, O. N. (2016). Ratings skills needed by business education graduates for entrepreneurial development in Southwest Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Development, Education and Science Research*, 4(1), 165-177.
- Gude, B. (2018). *Teach Yourself Computer: A Practical Approach to MS-Dos, MS-windows and MS word*. Port Harcourt: Upturn printers and publishers
- Hecker, I & Loprest, P. (2019). *Foundational Digital Skills for Career Progress*. <https://guardian.ng/appointments/close-education-employment-gap-to-prepare-youthsfor-4ir/>
- Helyer, N. C. & Lee, S. A. (2018). The effectiveness of computer assisted instruction in teaching introductory statistics. *Educational Technology and Society Journal*, 8 (2), 170 – 178
- Indeed Career Guide, (2021). Investigation into the factors that hinder the acquisition of competent entrepreneurial skills for effective business management among Business Education graduates in Nigeria. *Paper presented at the 22nd annual national conference of Business Educators of Nigeria, Abeokuta, Ogun State, 18thOctober*.
- International Telecommunication Union. (2018). *Digital skills toolkit*. [https:// www. itu .int/ aen/ ITU -D/ Digital -Inclusion/ Documents/ ITU %20Digital %20Skills %20Toolkit.pdf](https://www.itu.int/aen/ITU-D/Digital-Inclusion/Documents/ITU%20Digital%20Skills%20Toolkit.pdf)
- Kamalu, N. (2021). Extent of utilization of social software technologies for enhancing self-regulated learning by business education students in Anambra State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education (NIGJBED)*, 7(1), 401-415
- Muhammad, I. (2009). *Office administration and management technology (with practical auto-executive secretarial skills)*. Lagos: *Management and Business Associate-Services Corporate World Marketing Communication and Consult Limited*
- Norris, G. (2019). The place of office technology and management, curriculum and skills needed: A study in university of Sultan ZainalAbidin (Unisza), Malaysia. *Proceeding Technology*, 1(2), 234-249
- Nwafor, T. C. (2021). Essential soft skills for success in the twenty-first century workforce as perceived by business educators. *Delta PiEpsilon Journal*, 52, 43-53
- Nwagu, L. & Nwankwo, B. N. (2016). .Towards more effective vocationlization of business education in universities in south east Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*,6(25) 41-48.
- Nwokocha, P. I. (2021). Aims of business education. In Paul, E.O., Anioke, B.O., Enebe, P.A., Ezeagu, S.E. and Nwokocha, p. (2004). *Modern methods of teaching business courses*. Enugu: Modern Printers
- Oguejiofor, J & Umeh, C. N. (2016). *ICT and business education in a globalised economy*. Enugu: JTC publishers.
- Ojo, P. & Akhademe, G. (2016). Soft skills perceived by students and employers as relevant employability skills. Unpublished doctoral dissertations, Walden University. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations>
- Okeji, N. Nwankwo, H. Anene, J. & Olorunfemi, K. (2020). Utilization of digital skills for teaching and learning of business education in Public Universities in the South-South, Nigeria. *Journal of Business Educators of Nigeria Conference Proceedings* 8 (1) 367-377
- Oketoobo, G. Lawal, H. & Onipede, O. (2011). Developing soft skills measure in an Indonesian university: Procedure, Validity, and Reliability. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 1-8 10.18178/ijlt.2.2.140-147

- Olokor, G. (2022). 80% of Nigerian graduates unemployed-CIPM. The Punch. Retrieved on the 12th of April 2014 from www.punchng.com.
- Olukemi, J. O., & Boluwaji, C. E. (2018). Challenges of curriculum development in office technology and management in tertiary institutions. *International Journal of Technology and Inclusive Education (IJTIE)*, 1(3), 475-484.
- Olumese, H. K. & Ediagbonya, B. O. (2016). Business education in Nigeria: issues, challenges and way forward for national development. *Journal of Collaborative Research and Development (JCRD)*, 5 (1), 1-25
- Ovbiagele, A.O., & Mgbonyebi, D.O., (2019). Quality assurance and skill acquisition in OTM programme for national development. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*. 5(2), 63-75
- Oyinkoye, K. & Oluwalola, E. (2020). Skills, management of skills, and it skills requirements. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314417465>
- Round, M. (2018). Situated learning and teachers' digital competence. *Journal of Education & Information Technologies*, 13(4), 279-290
- Umeano N.E (2021). Digital skills required of business education graduates for employability in north-east Nigeria. *Journal of Business Educators of Nigeria Conference Proceedings* 8 (1) 400-406.
- UNESCO (2018). Digital skills critical for jobs and social inclusion. Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/news/digital-skills-critical-jobs-and-socialinclusion>
- UNICEF (2018). E-commerce can boost job creation and inclusive growth in developing countries. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/pressrelease/2019/11/23/e-commerce-can-boost-job-creation-and-inclusive-growth-in-developing-countries>
- Wickramasinghe, E. & Perera, H. (2010). Entrepreneurial skills needs of secretarial education graduates of colleges of education for self sustainability in Enugu State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management* 4(601- 607).
- Yamme, M. T. (2020). Lecturers' and students' perception on electronic learning as a new technology tool for studying business education in Nigerian universities in South-South State. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education* 1(3), 92 – 100